

Nutrient availability in soil and rice yield as influenced by presowing soil water treatments (average of 2 varieties).^a Maharashtra, India.

Treatment ^b	Available nutrients in soil (ppm)								Rice yield (t/ha)	
	15th day after soil water treatments				At sowing				Grain	Straw
	Nitro- gen	Phos- phorus	Iron	Man- ganese	Nitro- gen	Phos- phorus	Iron	Man- ganese		
<i>Presowing soil water treatments</i>										
Dry soil	76.6	10.70	2.63	4.58	83.71	11.64	2.89	4.93	2.61	2.87
Soil saturation	94.5	12.94	3.96	7.80	94.92	12.47	4.02	7.88	2.92	3.31
Soil submergence	107.2	13.22	4.78	8.64	97.70	13.05	4.83	8.75	3.12	3.42
“F” test	**	*	**	**	**	**	**	**	*	*
S.E. ±	2.5	0.58	0.28	0.33	1.33	0.19	0.24	0.32	0.11	0.12
C.D. at 5%	7.7	1.75	0.84	1.01	3.99	0.57	0.73	0.96	0.34	0.35
<i>Rice cultivars</i>										
Karjat 184									1.82	2.28
Tuljapur 1	No crop standing as nutrient availability in soil was studied up to sowing of rice.								3.94	4.16
“F” test									**	**
S.E. ±									0.09	0.09
C.D. at 5%									0.28	0.28

^aSignificance at the 1% (**) and 5% (*) levels. ^bInteraction between presowing soil water treatments and rice cultivars was nonsignificant.

during the early growth stages.

The tall, dryland cultivar Tuljapur 1

yielded significantly more grain and straw than Karjat 184. Dryland soil

conditions seem favorable to tall, dryland rice cultivars. ■

Relation of sowing time and seedling age to rice yields during rabi season

R. A. Khan and A. K. Swarnkar, Agronomy Division, M. P. Rice Research Institute, Labhandi, Raipur, India

The sowing time and age of rice seedlings must be adjusted carefully during the rabi season to obtain good seed germination and seedling growth during the initial stages when temperature is low and to facilitate early harvest before the rains begin.

An experiment in the 1978 rabi studied the effect of time of nursery sowing and seedling age on the yield of early-maturing rice varieties with and without foliar application of potash. The design was split plot with three replications. Three nursery sowing dates — 21 December, 28 December, and 4 January 1979 — and two seedling ages at transplanting (6 and 7 weeks) were in the main plots. Allocated each to subplot were two early-maturing semidwarf varieties, R155-2601 and Kalinga 2, and two potash application treatments (no foliar application and 1 foliar application, 1% concentration). Fertilizer was applied to all treatments at 80 kg N, 40 kg P₂O₅, and 30 kg K₂O/ha. Seedlings were

transplanted at a 20- x 10-cm spacing.

The effect of time of sowing on yield was highly significant. Sowing in the first week of January was superior to sowing in the third and fourth weeks of December (see table). That was because of low temperatures in the third week (25.4° C max, 8.2° C min) and the fourth (25.6° C max, and 8.1° C min) of December. The mean maximum and minimum temperatures from 4 to 10

January were 27.3° C and 10.5° C. Seedling age also gave significant differences. The 7-week-old seedlings performed better than the 6-week-old. Interaction between sowing time and seedling age was not significant.

Kalinga 2 gave significantly higher yields than R155-2601. The effect of foliar application of potash was not significant. ■

Effect of time of nursery sowing and seedling age on the yield of early-maturing rice varieties during the rabi season. Raipur, India, 1978–79.

Sowing date	Seedling age (wk)	Yield (t/ha)		
		R155-2601	Kalinga 2	Mean
21 Dec	6	0.92	1.05	0.99
	7	1.12	1.38	1.25
	Mean	1.02	1.22	1.12
28 Dec	6	0.95	1.20	1.08
	7	1.12	1.37	1.25
	Mean	1.04	1.29	1.16
4 Jan	6	1.16	1.53	1.35
	7	1.23	1.92	1.57
	Mean	1.19	1.73	1.46
Mean	6	1.01	1.26	1.14
	7	1.16	1.56	1.36
Overall mean		1.08	1.41	

For comparison of means of 2 sowing dates, CD at 5%
 For comparison of means of 2 seedling ages, CD at 5%
 For interaction (sowing date x seedling age), CD at 5%
 For comparison of means of 2 varieties, CD at 5%

210.
 172.
 not significant
 104.